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Is the residential sector ready for prescriptive maintenance? A short analysis.

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Existing facts

Repairing and maintaining obstacles:

lack of time, patience, and willingness

cheap market

lack of emotional attachment

Prescriptive maintenance (PsM)

main objectives:

- mitigates operational risks
- analyzes historical data and information
- provides expert advice and recommendations (prescriptions)
- prevents errors, failures, or operational breakdowns

PsM Techniques

Machine Learning (ML)

- > system anomalies prediction
- > failure detection
- > remaining useful life (RUL) estimation

Reinforcement Learning (RL)

- > automated decision-making

"Prescriptive maintenance does more than just predict failures, it proposes an optimal course of action."

Detected problem

- Recognized significance, but no visible implementation
- No sufficient research in the residential sector, as much as in manufacturing

Proposed solution

- Consideration of the global need for cost optimization and energy savings of households
- Potential prescriptions for PsM implementation

Sections

What we will talk about

01

Home Appliances Facts

02

**Home Appliances
Prescriptions**

03

Conclusions

Average Lifespan of an Appliance

Life cycle of most common home appliances

- short home appliance warranties
- phenomenon of 'nature' and 'nurture'
- emerging 'throw-away' culture

Common Home Appliance Problems

In case of electrical failures:

- energy waste
- increased energy bill
- serious damage to property and residents

- water that leaks under
- not enough cooling
- excessive ice accumulation
- light that doesn't turn on
- inability to function

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- stoppage at midcycle
 - water heating failure
 - unsatisfactory cleaning of dishes
 - light that doesn't turn on
 - weird sounds during operation
 - inability to function
 - function loss of lathering up the dishes inside

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- button malfunction
 - stoppage at midcycle
 - do not fill up
 - leaking
 - lint still appearing on washed cloths
 - no proper mix of soap and water
 - sudden operational alarming sounds

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- no preheating as it used to
 - taking longer to cook and bake
 - no working lights
 - obstructed electric or gas supply
 - inability to heat
 - broken clock

Home appliances maintenance habits

"Few residents have a maintenance routine and are aware of doing periodic maintenance."

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Home appliances good maintenance habits

"There is a variety of good maintenance habits to be applied regularly that may expand home appliance's lifetime while increasing their efficiency."

REFRIGERATOR AND FREEZER MAINTENANCE ACTIONS

Frequency	Maintenance Action
Once a year	Clean the flue, burner, baffle, fins and coils.
Once a year	Defrost the freezer.
Every 6 months	Clean behind and underneath your refrigerator using a vacuum cleaner.
Every three months	Clear and clean the drip openings.
Every three months	Clean the shelves inside the fridge, as well as the compartments, lining, and door gasket.
Every month	Check your temperature settings to keep food fresh.
Regularly	Dust the sides and top.
Every time	Wipe up spills quickly to prevent staining and odors.
Every time	Avoid packing items too tightly for proper cooling functionality.

Home appliances good maintenance habits

- lifespan extension

OVEN MAINTENANCE ACTIONS

Frequency	Maintenance Action
At least once yearly	Clean behind and underneath the unit using a vacuum cleaner attachment.
Every 1-3 months	Clean the oven racks.
Every 1-3 months	Check your oven door gasket (seal).
Regularly	Clean range hoods regularly with soapy water.
Regularly	Clean the stove-top and oven.
Regularly	Clean or change the range hood exhaust filters.
Every time	Avoid using very heavy or large pots and pans.
Every time	Self-cleaning function.
Every time	Use a surge protector.
Every time	Don't overfill the oven.

Home appliances good maintenance habits

BENEFITS

- lifespan extension
- energy consumption improvement

WASHING MACHINE MAINTENANCE ACTIONS

Frequency	Maintenance Action
Once per month	Use a cleaner on the inside of the washing machine tubs and clean out the fabric softener dispenser.
Every month	Check your washing machine's water hoses for signs of wear or weakness.
Every time	keep the machine as close to the floor as possible.
Every time	Clean it outside and avoid spilling soap or other products on the washer.
Every time	Avoid overloading the machine.

Home appliances good maintenance habits

BENEFITS

- lifespan extension
- energy consumption improvement
- wear and tear slow down

WATER HEATER MAINTENANCE ACTIONS

Frequency	Maintenance Action
Every 10 years	Replace your water heater if it is more than 10 years old.
Once	Lower the thermostat.
Once	Insulate storage tank and do not cover the heater's thermostat, burner, and the top and bottom.
Once	Install heat traps.
Once	Install a timer to turn off the heater.
Once	Insulate hot and cold water pipes connected to the unit.
Every year	Drain the tank.
Regularly	Use cold water.
Regularly	Repair leaky faucets.

Home appliances good maintenance habits

BENEFITS

- lifespan extension
- energy consumption improvement
- wear and tear slow down
- mainly completed by homeowners

ELECTRIC IRON MAINTENANCE ACTIONS

Frequency	Maintenance Action
Regularly	Descale the device.
Every time	Wipe the iron plate right before the use.
Every time	Start cleaning the iron plate only after it cools off.
Every time	Remove any leftover water from the container after ironing.
Every time	Avoid rubbing the iron plate against sharp surfaces.
Every time	Avoid using strong chemicals intended for metals.

Home appliances good maintenance habits

BENEFITS

- lifespan extension
- energy consumption improvement
- wear and tear slow down
- mainly completed by homeowners
- specific professional interventions

MICROWAVE MAINTENANCE ACTIONS

Frequency	Maintenance Action
Periodically	Keep up with easy replacements such as light bulbs, door latches, turntables, turntable motors, and charcoal filters.
Regularly	Clean the microwave.
Regularly	Try preprogrammed cooking times.
Every time	Avoid running on empty.
Every time	Respect weight limitations.
Every time	Guard against surges.
Every time	Use microwave safe dishware.

Home appliances good maintenance habits

BENEFITS

- lifespan extension
- energy consumption improvement
- wear and tear slow down
- mainly completed by homeowners
- specific professional interventions

DRYER MAINTENANCE ACTIONS

Frequency	Maintenance Action
At least once a year	Clean out the exhaust vent system.
Once every three months	Vacuum behind and underneath the dryer.
Regularly	Clean the exterior of the dryer and the door opening.
Every time	Clean the lint filter after the load.

Home appliances good maintenance habits

AIR CONDITIONING MAINTENANCE ACTIONS

Frequency	Maintenance Action
Once a year	Professional system maintenance service one month before the cooling season begins.
Periodically	Straighten any bent condensing unit fins.
Periodically	Check insulation and replace if it has fallen off of feed lines.
Periodically	Create shade for the outdoor unit.
Regularly	Clean and check water drain and the outside condenser unit.
Every month	Check your filters, clean or replace as needed.
Every time	Keep the condensing unit free of any debris.
Every time	Make sure registers are not blocked.

DISHWASHER MAINTENANCE ACTIONS

Frequency	Maintenance Action
Periodically	Remove any mineral deposits from the heating element with vinegar.
Periodically	To minimize soap film, wash with a rinse solution.
Regularly	Clean the spray arm to prevent soap build-up.
Regularly	Inspect the floor near the dishwasher for water stains or other signs of leaking.
Regularly	Inspect the floor near the dishwasher for water stains or other signs of leaking.
Every time	Keep dishes clear of the spray arm.
Every time	Load the dishwasher according to the manufacturer's recommendations.
Every time	Only run when the dishwasher is full.
Every time	Do not use more (or less) detergent than is recommended.
Every time	Load fragile dishes on the top rack.
Every time	Reduce suds in the dishwasher by using soap crystals instead of liquid detergent.

TRUTH ABOUT MAINTENANCE

How Maintenance Habits make the difference

WHAT PROFESSIONALS DO

Repairment
Maintenance

↑ COSTS

↑ EFFICIENCY

WHAT OWNERS DO

Maintenance

↓ COSTS

↑ EFFICIENCY

To repair or to replace?

PROS of repair (motives)

- life extension of household appliances
- more viable strategy (i.e., economically)
- positive prior experiences
- emotional attachment
- extended use of appliances
- environmental reasons
- high quality

CONS of repair (barriers)

- convenience
- repair quality
- lack of information
- cost
- time
- obsolescence
- previous unpleasant experiences

"Vast majority of consumers do not repair their broken home appliances."

Optimal replacement of appliances from an environmental perspective - Extending product use-times or early replacement by energy-efficient appliances

From an environmental point of view, it is recommended to use these appliances as long as possible

From an environmental point of view, it may be worthwhile to replace these appliances prematurely with a new device of the highest energy efficiency class.

* Replace only after a defect

Home appliance's reliability

"it's critical to strike the appropriate balance between energy efficiency and initial price"

the "energy efficiency gap"

the slow uptake of energy-efficient technologies

How much energy could a grade 1 electrical appliance save?

Household Appliances	Grade 1 vs grade 3	Grade 1 vs grade 5
Window Type Air Conditioner	11%	25%
Split Type Air Conditioner	36%	61%
Refrigerator	41%	97%
Washer	23%	48%

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Conclusions

CONCLUSIONS

take home
messages

"The findings of this paper reveal that in general, including all sectors, PsM is not a mature and ready-to-apply concept."

CONCLUSIONS

take home
messages

"There is only one suggested framework for residential PsM not yet tested in a real-life application."

CONCLUSIONS

take home
messages

"There is a plethora of benefits
when applying PsM."

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PRECEPT

Less Energy > Smarter Buildings

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